

SEMANTICS OF ARTICLES EXPRESSING NUMBER AND QUANTITY

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ABSTRACT

Proverbs are phrases or sentences created by the people on the basis of life experience, which usually have an instructive content, have a concise image, complete meaning and wisdom. The more we study these proverbs and sayings, the less we learn them, because through proverbs we feel the whole life activity of our ancestors, their feelings, dreams and thoughts, and draw conclusions from them as necessary. Also, among our proverbs, we use numbers and quantities as examples and comparisons to express our effectiveness. This article is based on a number of scientific observations about proverbs expressing number and quantity, their meaning, content, and use.

Every nation strives to gain a deeper understanding of its spiritual and educational values, to learn more about its history. Also, the unique customs, traditions, nationality, value of each nation and people were formed from the times when this nation was formed, that is, it began to be formed, or even earlier. It is these customs and ceremonies that show who the people are. As the writer Togay Murad said: "What is the people with the people! People with their traditions! People with their national traditions left from their ancestors!" [1. 47 b] And proverbs show us the innermost customs, traditions, ceremonies, feelings, legends, narratives, behavior, life, labor activity, the total material and spiritual world of the ancient Uzbek people. will deliver. The advantages of proverbs in this regard are: A proverb has an effective and concise form rather than an idea expressed through a simple word or sentence, as well as being given in the direction of a conclusion, a verdict, i.e., it cannot be rejected, it can be accepted directly. It occupies an important place in our language as a paremiological unit. Also, to express the quantity, the following proverbs are often repeated today by our people:

- Trust one eye more than two ears.
- A single mind is good, two are even better.
- Get out of your hands, get out of the way.
- Seven neighborhood parents per child.
- One death per head.
- A hundred sorrows do not finish a job.

- A bullet kills one, a word kills a thousand.
- One goat is blind, it is awesome.
- When three people are one, one is alone.
- If you cut one, plant ten. Trust one eye more than two ears.
- A single mind is good, two are even better.
- Get out of your hands, get out of the way.
- Seven neighborhood parents per child.
- One death per head.
- A hundred sorrows do not finish a job.
- A bullet kills one, a word kills a thousand.
- One goat is blind, it is awesome.
- When three people are one, one is alone.
- If you cut one, plant ten.en.

We can say that every Uzbek citizen has said or heard such proverbs at least once in his life. Expressing such a strong judgment, it affects the feelings of the listener and makes him tremble.

All the power of the word is reflected in the thought and meaning expressed through such proverbs. Such proverbs can be used figuratively or in their own sense.

Proverbs expressing number and quantity appear both in the form of a compound sentence and sometimes in the form of a simple sentence. Already in the 11th century, M. Kashgari included a large part of the wise sayings of the Turkic peoples in his "Devon" and explained in Arabic the meaning and context of their use. More than 300 pieces of poetry, 291 proverbs and sayings related to folk oral works are presented in "Devonu lug'otit turk".

Later, in Uzbek linguistics, folk proverbs began to be studied in a different direction, that is, in many works on the language and style of the works of writers and poets, special attention was paid to studying the spiritual and methodological features of folk proverbs in candidate dissertations. . In this regard, A. Rustamov, H. Sulayman, Sh. Shomaksudov, Sh. [3.] 85-87 b] can be cited. The important task of creating a complete synonym dictionary of folk proverbs in Uzbek linguistics was accomplished by B. Joraeva. The term "proverb" is derived from the Arabic word qawlun-to speak, to say. The idea expressed through a proverb has a strong impact on a person and becomes an undeniable truth, so attention to this genre is strong. "A proverb is equivalent to at least one sentence, has the character of a sentence, expresses a grammatical idea, is always equal to a sentence in terms of its internal grammatical construction, the content understood from it is revealed only in a figurative way."

But among the proverbs, the types that express such a quantitative relationship are of special importance. As Jalaluddin Rumi said: "The value of any "thing" is determined by its quantity, it is impossible to describe something that does not have a quantity. God made this world that was created dark so that the light could be revealed."

Such a concept of conflict and contradiction is also found in the lexical-semantic basis of proverbs. The instructive thought given through such proverbs has a stronger effect on a person. It fills him with thoughts, makes him think. Here are some examples of adverbs expressing number and quantity:

- There is a difference from word to word, there are thirty-two prices.
- Master one craft before you can play a hundred crafts.
- Buy ten and one blind.
- Between six fists.
- You can tie a hundred bags, but not a hundred mouths.
- A boy needs one, a girl needs a hundred
- I greeted the Uzbek and received ten coins as compensation.
- The owner gets a thousand coins, the thief one coin.
- Don't count eight.
- The sustenance of one who wakes up in the morning is eight.
- One mountain will take the place of seven fathers.

To conclude, differential symbols in proverbs increase the meaning and scope of proverbs. The sphere of influence on a person is stronger and more colorful than a simple word or sentence, it expresses artistry, sounds concise and resounding in the direction of conclusion. The abundance of such proverbs in our language is a proof that the Uzbek people have seen a lot, and their life experience is extremely high. Also, using our thoughts once again in such proverbs and trying to find the essence of it is a sign that we follow all the great and noble sayings of our forefathers and ancestors and look at them with respect.

It can be seen from this that respecting the elders and following the teachings of the ancestors are sacred feelings embedded in the blood of the Uzbek people. Therefore, in the process of speaking, it is necessary to pay attention to the appropriate use of words and their stylistic color.

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